

Descriptive Study of The Nature of Educational Science

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ABSTRAK

A review of the nature of education is a review that must be holistic. A holistic review regarding the nature of education is needed considering that education is a universal thing that cannot be separated from human life. This article was written using a qualitative approach supported by using a literature study method by reviewing literature related to the theme of the article. From the results of the study, it is clear that the field of study of educational science is the educational situation. The method used is an empirical method, equipped with rational and transcendental analysis, to open the horizon of meaning of educational phenomena. The recognition that education is a science has implications for educational practice for both educational scientists and anyone working in the field of education. In the end, educational science is useful for human welfare because educational science cannot be separated from studying and researching the role of values and norms in human life, especially educational activities themselves.

INTRODUCTION

God has created humans as intelligent creatures. By having reason, humans can be called the most perfect creatures when compared to other creatures created by God. With reason, humans are able to utilize all their potential in order to live their lives better. As creatures (who) are intelligent, it is inevitable that humans will always become better people in the future, both materially and morally. Utilizing reason well and appropriately is the main essence of education.

Education itself - broadly means all forms of life experiences in various living environments that produce a positive influence on individual humans. Education has the same goal as the goal of human life itself, where it is subjective, and lasts throughout life and is multidimensional. By understanding the goals of education, you will gain an understanding that education is actually a complex concept. The complexity of education is what causes education to have various meanings and forms.

However, from various things related to the meaning of education, many people believe that education is a universal concept. Education is inherent in human life wherever and whenever. Education is an effort to humanize humans by means of which they cannot be separated from the position of human reason. Thus, the development of reason (intellectualism) needs to continue. An educated mind will enable humans to develop their potential to a better – and higher – level, which in turn will become a perfect human being (Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia, 2012). With reason, humans will affirm their existence as Rene Descarter said "Cogito Ergo Sum", "I think therefore I am". The absence of reason will mean that humans will not have any legal implications for it (Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia, 2012).

Not only at the individual human level, education also has an important essence in a community. Education can maintain and disseminate various basic values held by a society. Furthermore, education is the basic foundation for the development of a society within the scope of a nation and state. Without education, a nation and state will live in a condition of decline which can also be accompanied by moral decay. Under these conditions, education (once again)

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occupies a vital role which needs to be made into a common agenda of the people of a nation and state to be carried out in accordance with its basic foundations.

Thus, a review of the nature of education is a review that must be holistic. A holistic review regarding the nature of education is needed considering that education is a universal thing that cannot be separated from human life. A holistic review is needed because on many occasions people often forget the meaning and essence of education itself because education is so embedded in human life that it is considered just a routine of ordinary value. Thus, this article tries to reflect back on the basic meaning and essence of education, especially how education itself is understood as science. Furthermore, it is not only limited to a reflective review of the nature (knowledge) of education but can also be a form of real action related to the nature of education itself.

METHOD

The writing of this article uses an analytical descriptive method based on extracting data through the method of literature study/literature study from several sources of literature (written). Writing is done through a process of extracting data from various reference sources which discuss various articles/writings related to various literature on the nature of educational science. These various sources are published in public media, so that they can be accessed openly through various places (libraries) and internet media. This paper can be an elaboration of various related articles and writings. Likewise, this article is more of a synthesis of existing writings, to be seen later in relation to what can be done in the current context

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Education, Science, and Educational Science

Etymologically, there are many equivalent words that have the same meaning as the word "education". For example, the words education in English, ta'lim, tarbiyah, and ta'dib in Arabic, didik in Malay, and the word *pelipawentah* in Javanese (Hidayat & Abdillah, 2019). The diversity of equivalents of these words is basically not a problem because in substance each of these words still defines education as an effort to guide, train, teach, even with other words that have the same meaning (Ishak, 1995). Terminologically, education can be interpreted as conscious and planned activities carried out by at least two people by creating the right atmosphere and learning process as the main basis. Educational activities aim to develop all human potential (students) in order to achieve maturity in all aspects of life (Supardi, 2019).

Meanwhile, etymologically, science also has several equivalent words that have the same meaning. For example, the word 'ilm in Arabic, the word science in English, and also the word *scientia* in Latin. Science (often combined with knowledge) is a conscious effort to improve human rational abilities from various aspects of reality in the realm of human life. Science is a summary of knowledge that has been tested systematically using a certain methodology (Soelaiman, 2019). Science is a concept that is formed from human efforts to use their minds to explore further the knowledge they have. From this meaning, a simple understanding can then be drawn that knowledge is an integral part related to human life and education itself.

Science begins its journey by starting with human experience and will also stop at the limits of human experience. Science - even though it is universal, is limited to different things in human experience because science has a function as a tool to solve various problems experienced by humans. Furthermore, science limits the scope of its exploration to human experience because science must be empirical based on scientific methods, something that human experience which is abstract in nature does not have. Limitations in human experience do not negate the journey of science to continue to develop beyond human experience. Science is developing very rapidly and giving rise to many branches, even though it is based on two large poles of science, namely natural and human-social (Suriasomantri, 1996; Prayogi, 2022).

On the other hand, education has *de facto* existed since the existence of humans themselves. Before the existence of educational science, humans had made efforts to educate based on instinct, empirical experience, and not based on theoretical abstractions about education. It can be said that education is general - based on reality, something that humans

have done widely since humans themselves have been on the face of the earth. Education based on instinct and experience is what, at a certain historical point, then develops into a science with various derivatives systematically. In summary, it can be said that educational science is the study of (related to) education from a broad perspective. Educational science is a science that studies various problems that arise in educational practice in human life (Hamalik, 2010). However, the review of education as a *de jure* science can be said to have its starting point in Western Europe, especially in the Netherlands in 1925. Pioneered by a pedagogical expert, M.J. Langeveld, education is officially recognized as a science.

Education can become a scientific discipline because it has a systematic object of study, methods and presentation. Apart from that, education as a science must have several characteristics, including: First, empirical. This is because the object is subjective in the world of experience. Second, spiritual. This is because the educational situation is based on human goals which do not leave students to their natural conditions. Third, normative. This is because it is based on choosing between good and bad. Fourth, history, because it provides theoretical descriptions of various educational systems historically by considering the background and cultural philosophy that was influential in a particular era. Fifth, practical. This is because, as a science, education provides thinking about educational problems and provisions which are directly aimed at educational actions (Hidayat & Abdillah, 2019).

Education as an independent science has its own scope which is different from other sciences. The scope of educational science is the educational situation. Educational situations mean agogic, namely in situations that contain efforts to influence, guide, provide assistance, teach values and norms of life ethically, from educators to students. Furthermore, through the philosophy of science, educational science also has a scope of axiology, epistemology and ontology that is different from other sciences (Hendrowibowo, 1994).

The axiological scope in educational science is the existence of use values for the benefit of human welfare both physically and psychologically. This is because it is impossible for educational science to separate itself from studying and researching the role of values and norms in human life, especially in educational activities. In the scope of epistemology, educational science is not only limited to the use of empirical methods to understand the nature of educational efforts themselves. The use of empirical methods (as a characteristic of science) must be equipped with rational and transcendental analysis so that educational science can reveal the essence of educational efforts in a substantial and holistic manner. In the ontological scope, educational science emphasizes its position as something empirical because it has objects in the form of educational actions that exist in human life experience. By understanding the position of educational science well, humans can provide complete interpretations of various educational phenomena, and not be satisfied with mere visible observations. To be able to understand the nature of educational efforts, people need to critically review the various reasons and goals of educators for acting both in the classroom and outside the classroom in situations and conditions associated with the teaching and learning process and the goals to be achieved (Hendrowibowo, 1994).

Perspectives and Objects of Educational Study

Education is a basic or essential phenomenon in human life. Where there is life, there must be education. Education is a symptom as well as human power and efforts to humanize themselves. In subsequent developments, demands emerged for education to be better, so that human potential could continue to be developed. From this, various perspectives and objectives of educational science emerge (Prayogi, 2021).

There are at least two perspectives in viewing educational science (or also known as pedagogy) as an applied-practical science related to human activity, namely educating and being educated, namely theoretical and practical perspectives. First, theoretical educational science, which is an effort to organize problems and knowledge about education scientifically, which moves from practice to theoretical development to the education system. Thus, philosophical studies can also be included in the study of theoretical educational science. Theoretical educational science requires people to educate as best as possible for educational success,

whereby interactions between educators and students occur actively, consciously, and appropriately on various matters related to education normatively. In this case then, theoretical educational science (also) is normative. Normatively, it must also be ethical and creative, because theoretical education is related to efforts to develop humans with certain ideals and norms (ideals). Furthermore, theoretical educational science can also be called practical anthropological educational science because it provides a rational and systematic understanding of human matters regarding how education is carried out by following certain human rules (Hendrowibowo, 1994).

Second, practical educational science is an effort aimed at various ways of moving/acting in educational situations aimed at implementing the ideals previously stated in theoretical educational science. In this case, practice is carried out when the theory has been previously understood. However, educational science does not only carry out scientific-theoretical activities, but also seeks to improve and develop various educational practices, especially those related to formal educational practices such as in school institutions. Various educational practices in formal school institutions, such as planning, curriculum implementation, supervision, evaluation and so on are the scope of study in practical educational science. With it, practical educational science (also) becomes pure science. As a pure science, practical educational science is actually also theoretical because it contains various proportional concepts which must always be tested in empirical realities, or through educational practices which are then systematically developed new theories, either in the form of new theories or development of theories. existing ones (Hendrowibowo, 1994).

If these two perspectives are connected, then theory has the benefit of increasing understanding and comprehension of education. It doesn't stop there, by connecting these two perspectives, there will be evaluations and corrections in educational efforts so that improvements and improvements in educational methods emerge, and also from educators themselves. Thus, practice is carried out using theoretical guidance. Educational practice that is guided by theory will produce or develop theories that can be used to evaluate or improve existing theories.

Apart from perspective, education as a science also has an object of study. In this case, there are two kinds of educational science objects, namely material objects and formal objects (Pidarta, 2009). First, material objects. A material object is material that is used as a research review or can form knowledge related to students and their learning community. Material objects can also be interpreted as things that are studied, focused on, or investigated by a scientific discipline, which includes various things, both concrete and abstract, material and immaterial. It can also be in the form of various ideas, problems, concepts and so on. Material objects can also be referred to as the substance of the problem (subject matter) (Usman, 2008).

In this case then, the material objects in educational science are things related to the material material that is subject to education, or related to all aspects that are the direct field of study of educational science, which in this case are students and learning citizens. Material objects in educational science are one aspect of education which, if viewed from this point of view, educational science can be divided into two. First, macro educational science, which means a comprehensive, integrated review of all educational activities in order to achieve national goals. Second, micro educational science, which means the study of educational activities as a whole or can be one form of educational activity itself. However, it is also worth paying attention to, that the objects - and also including materials - in educational sciences are the same as other social (and natural) sciences, which make humans the material objects (and at the same time subjects) (Anggraeni, 2020).

On the other hand, the formal object in educational science is the aspect of education itself, which in this case can be seen in a very broad, narrow and limited scope. Formal objects in a very broad scope, in education, mean the learning experiences experienced by every human being in their lives which influence the growth and development of their lives. In a narrow scope, the formal object of educational science is the school as a formal educational institution whose existence is sought by humans. Finally, the formal object of educational science in a limited broad scope means various learning experiences in human life, both in formal and

informal educational institutions which are carried out in order to achieve certain goals (Mudyahardjo, 2006).

The formal object of educational science also means symptoms that are seen, felt, experienced and expressed in human life. Formal objects mean various approaches carefully and gradually seen from the aspects of material objects and according to individual abilities. In other words, the formal object is the point of view from which the material object is seen. Formal objects in this case not only provide a complete picture of scientific buildings, but can also differentiate them from other scientific buildings as well. In short, the formal object of educational science can provide a variety of viewpoints as a whole from certain aspects (Usman, 2008; Syarifudin, 2006).

Collaboratively, formal and material objects in educational science can be differentiated into three views, including, first, education as a human phenomenon. This can be seen from the interaction between educational components (in the form of goals, students, educators, and the environment) in achieving goals. Second, education as a conscious effort. This can be seen from various efforts to foster creativity, preserve values, and prepare educated and productive human workers. Third, education as a human phenomenon and a conscious effort to prepare for the human future. This can then be seen from the ways to deal with life's problems and how to analyze them from various time dimensions (Anggraeni, 2020).

Aims and Implications of Educational Science

To develop educational science, educational science needs to have a goal that is oriented towards the truth of educational science itself. In this way, educational science will develop into two orientations. First, educational science will focus on the truth of a science itself. With this view, educational science will produce pure theoretical science that focuses on science and ignores the practical aspects of science. However, on the other hand, educational science will also be oriented towards the practical development of knowledge that can be used in educational practice in human life. This means that orientation and goals in educational science are like two sides of a coin that complement each other, where educational science has the aim of being able to be put into practice based on theoretical matters that have been studied purely.

It also needs to be emphasized that the aim of educational science is not the question of whether or not there is influence of educational activities, but rather the effort to gain an understanding of various facts related to education. Educational science aims to provide various information and explanations about the various basics of education in various educational situations, types and pathways in educational levels to provide students with provisions for a better life in the future. This means that educational science provides information about problems, causes and provision efforts for educators to educate the next generation. If the absorption of all information related to education can be carried out well by all interested parties, especially educators and students, then the educational process will be quickly conveyed and well absorbed, especially by students. On the contrary, if educators do not have enough educational knowledge, it will affect efforts to deliver it well to students.

Educational science is intended to provide information or data about various basics of education in various conditions such as those related to the type of education, educational path, and level of education. Students must be given the freedom to pursue cultural activities, in order to create greater independence in the future. Providing information here means providing descriptions of problems, causes and possibilities in efforts and provisions for educators to educate the next generation. The useful value of educational science is disseminated for the benefit of physical and spiritual human welfare. Educational science cannot possibly escape from studying and researching the role of various values and norms in human life, especially in educational activities (Siswoyo, 1996).

Apart from that, the aim of educational science is not to focus on the influence of educators' activities, but rather on efforts to gain an understanding regarding various facts. In this case, the function of educational science is related to its position as part of science itself, which in this case has the function of providing careful consideration to the contents of

educational theory, the suitability between theory and practice, as well as the meanings contained therein.

On the other hand, education itself has the aim of making humans transitive, which means humans have the ability to perceive and respond to environmental problems and the ability to dialogue not only with each other, but also with the world and all its contents. Furthermore, it is said that education must also equip humans with the ability to defend themselves against the increasingly strong tendency of industrial culture, even though this culture can raise human living standards (Pidarta, 2009). Education aims to provide life experiences for students, facilitate various scientific activities, provide services for developing abilities and interests, facilitate the use of good learning methods, provide individual freedom, provide love for others, and the importance of maintaining relationships between teachers and students. educate. So, the aim of education is none other than developing students' potential naturally, in the sense of giving them the opportunity to develop their potential as it is. It does not need to be directed in a certain direction for the benefit of the group. In this way, education only provides assistance or services by preparing everything necessary and providing sufficient guidance. It is hoped that students can achieve their complete educational goals.

Furthermore, the goals of education are closely related to the expected changes in students after experiencing the educational process, both individual behavior and personal life as well as the life of the community in the natural surroundings where the individual lives. Educational objectives are a set of educational outcomes achieved by students after carrying out educational activities. All educational activities, such as guidance, teaching, or training, are directed to achieve educational goals. In this context, educational goals are a component of the education system that occupies a central position and function. That is why every teaching staff needs to understand well the goals of education (Suardi, 2010; Maunah, 2009).

In practice, education, especially in educational institutions, has several goals that bridge the progress of universal educational goals, namely, first; Education has the general goal of enlightening the life of (a nation) and developing people who have faith and are devoted to God, have noble character, have knowledge and skills, physical and spiritual health, a stable and independent personality and have social and national responsibility. Second, education has institutional goals, namely goals that are the task of certain educational institutions to achieve. In this case, it can be seen in the educational practices carried out by formal educational institutions, for example the educational objectives at the primary level are different from the educational objectives at the secondary level, and so on. If all (formal) educational institutions can achieve their goals, this means that the goals of education have been achieved. Third, education has curricular goals, which in this case take the form of goals in a field of study or subject, for example learning goals for Social Sciences, Indonesian or Mathematics. In this case, to achieve the desired goals, each educational institution needs to use a certain curriculum design (Purwanto, 2011).

From the various explanations above, there is a clear and fundamental difference between the aims of educational science and the aims of education. The aim of education is focused on preparing professional educators. Meanwhile, the goal of education is aimed at developing students' abilities to achieve optimal self-development (Suryapermana & Imroatun, 2017).

Apart from the objectives, both education and educational science have implications for educational practice for educators, educational reviewers or anyone working in the field of education. Some of these implications include first, educational science or anyone who works in the field of education, needs to understand conceptually the nature of education as a science which also includes the characteristics of educational science. Understanding this will help parties involved in education to be able to carry out their educational duties well. Second, by having a good and correct understanding of the concepts and characteristics of educational science, it is hoped that all parties involved in it will have the awareness and willingness to participate in developing educational science in the ideal direction. Third, the development of educational science in an ideal direction requires the importance of the parties involved in education to have academic confidence, to truly develop educational science based on various

applicable scientific moral principles and scientific ethics. This can be seen in the practice of developing educational science which should be carried out in the context of seeking the truth, carried out with full honesty, relying on rational arguments, not degrading human honor, dignity and nature and so on. Because, if these things are not done, then the efforts of the parties involved in education will only result in futility (Sukadari & Sulistyono, 2017).

Apart from that, other implications for understanding education as a science include emphasizing that education must have a focus on students' subjects. This means that students are treated as subjects. Education is carried out in accordance with the development and abilities of students, and in the process and results, education can develop students' abilities as a whole. Education also needs to be developed into a scientific (theoretical) concept and religious humanist practice. Humanist education which focuses on aspects of individual freedom must be integrated with religious education in order to build an individual (social) life that has freedom and independence, but without abandoning the religious values followed by the community, or rejecting divine values (atheism). Furthermore, with this integration, education will place humans at the center, but be controlled by religious values. This includes deliberative educational policies as an implication of understanding education as a science, which means there is a desire to increase the intensity of community participation in the process of forming aspirations and opinions so that the resulting educational policies are closer to the expectations of all parties involved. Intensifying the deliberation process through public discourse ensures that the impact of the policies made has optimal results, namely being useful for improving collective welfare, respecting human dignity and becoming more just (Wasitohadi, 2012).

Methods and Systematics of Educational Science

Education can be categorized as a science (knowledge), one of which is because it has a scientific method. The method itself is a way/stage to achieve a goal using a predetermined path. The scientific method plays a role at the level of transformation from the form of knowledge to knowledge. A knowledge can become a science by depending on the scientific method. This is because the scientific method is a standard for assessing and measuring the suitability of a science (from previously being knowledge). A phenomenon of knowledge that is logical, but not empirical, also cannot be included in the category of science, but falls into the area of philosophy. Thus, the scientific method is always supported by two pillars of integrative knowledge, namely ratios and facts (Prayogi, 2023).

Education as a branch of science means that science is always experiencing development, especially in terms of scientific thinking activities surrounding education. In terms of methods, educational scientific thinking emphasizes a process of thought and investigation that uses certain methods and methods that contain processes/stages of investigation that include scope, problem, objective, hypothesis, research location, research subject, research object, research instrument. data about the variables studied, and data analysis and conclusions. Thus, an understanding can be drawn that educational methods are a set of methods, stages and paths used by educators in the learning process so that students can achieve learning goals or master certain competencies that have been formulated in a syllabus.

Regarding methods, educational science has several methods that are used as a way to achieve goals in education. First is the Normative method. This method is related to the concept of the perfect human being that education wants to achieve. This method also answers questions related to the issue of values, which in this case are good values and bad values. Second, the explanatory method. This method is related to the question of what conditions and forces make an educational process successful. In this case, educational science gets help from various theories about education which may be produced by various other sciences. A practical recommendation for educators must be based on a correct understanding of the nature of students, their development, the ways they learn and the ways they respond to social influences. A good and correct educational theory provides an adequate explanation regarding what happens in nature, which is based on empirical evidence. Third, technological methods. This method has the function of revealing how something (in the educational aspect) is done in order to achieve successful achievement of the desired goals. Fourth, descriptive-phenomenological

method. This method attempts to analyze various educational realities and then codify and classify them so that the true reality is found. Fifth, the hermeneutical method. This method seeks to understand concrete and historical educational realities to explain the meaning and structure of educational activities. Sixth, critical-philosophical analysis method. This method seeks to critically analyze various terms, questions, concepts and theories that exist or are used in education (Said, 1989; Soedomo, 1990).

Another important thing related to methods in educational science is the need to increase students' understanding of the educational process. From this it can be said that a method is said to be effective if the method can help students understand the educational process well. Whatever the method, the goal is to make students understand the ongoing educational process. It is also ideal that good methods in education can create various positive conditions in learning, such as making students challenged. In this case, the method chosen must be able to provide space for students to express themselves in solving problems. Apart from that, the method chosen is also expected to build students' curiosity. Curiosity is the beginning of knowledge. Curiosity needs to be cultivated through the right methods too (Marianingsih and Hidayati, 2018: 11-12).

Apart from methods, systematic thinking is also needed so that education can become a scientific science. This means that scientific thinking in the process must be imbued with ideas that are arranged sequentially and united according to a paradigmatic framework. Education as a human phenomenon can be analyzed based on the educational process or situation, namely when there is interaction between components (goals, students, educators, tools and environment). Several systematics in educational science include the first systematic, where education becomes a symptom that can be analyzed from the educational process or situation. In this case, in the educational aspect there are various components that interact in an integrated manner with each other in a series of unified wholes in achieving goals. Among the various components of education include educational objectives, students, educators, educational content, educational methods, educational tools, and educational environment. The second systematic, which makes education a conscious effort to develop the personality and abilities of students or humans at large. This second systematic starts from the function of education, namely fostering students' creativity (creativity education), preserving human and divine values (morality education), and preparing a productive workforce (productivity education). The third systematic, which means that education is seen as a human phenomenon as well as a conscious effort to anticipate the context of socio-cultural development in the future (Siswoyo, Hadisusanto, & Sidharto, Introduction to Educational Science, 1995).

Related to this systematics, educational science inherently has dimensions that can be seen as part of the systematics of educational science, including; First, the dimensions of the educational environment. In this case, the educational environment consists of the family education environment, the school education environment, and the out-of-school education environment (education in the community). Second, the dimensions of the types of educational problems. In this case, what is included in this dimension includes substantive problems (theoretical problems in education), structural problems (problems with the structure of educational institutions), and operational problems (practical problems in education). Third, the dimensions of time and space. This means, apart from analyzing various educational problems faced in society today, efforts are also needed to study various educational problems that have existed in society in the past, and in the future. Armed with wisdom extracted from the historical treasures of education (education in the past) and comparative education (knowledge of educational practices) in other countries, it will be possible to face today's educational problems with a better outlook and attitude. scientific and more professional. The educational problems that will occur in society in the future can only be predicted, they cannot be known precisely. Accuracy in predicting future problems is largely determined by the ability to understand present and past situations and problems deeply and essentially, both in one's own society and in other societies (Buchori, 1994).

CONCLUSION

The essence of education is a comprehensive review of aspects of human life that displays educational concepts. Therefore, a review of the nature of education actually revolves around many aspects. The essence of education talks about the educational process which is never separated from human life. Education is a unique property and a tool for humans. Education itself is used as a tool to survive and adapt to the surrounding environment. Education is also a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential. Education is not just a transfer of information, knowledge and skills, but also a reference for human values. Human values are more directed to character and personality. Education is not only related to the past and present, but is more concerned with human life in the future. Thus, education is carried out now, with the capital of past experience, to be directed at the future. For this reason, education must focus attention on future problems

To be able to focus attention on future problems, education developed into a science. Educational science is a science that discusses general educational problems in a comprehensive and abstract manner. It is also critical, methodical and systematic scientific thinking about education. Educational science is an independent science that has objects and study methods that are different from other sciences such as sociology, cultural studies and anthropology. The field of study in educational science is the educational situation. The method used is an empirical method, equipped with rational and transcendental analysis, to open the horizon of meaning of educational phenomena. The recognition that education is a science has implications for educational practice for both educational scientists and anyone working in the field of education. In the end, educational science is useful for human welfare because educational science cannot be separated from studying and researching the role of values and norms in human life, especially educational activities themselves.

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